

IN KINDERGARTEN AND THE PRIMARY GRADES TO TEACH MATHEMATICS AND SCIENCE AMONG THE COMPETITION

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ANOTATSIYA

In kindergarten and primary school mathematics teaching them the important role of the education process because it is able to deep readers of this subject o'rgatilmashligi next qiyinlashtradi science so'ndradi interest to their readers. The results of mathematical knowledge slowing educational level goes down. Mathematical knowledge is important to a man.

Keywords: Preparatory groups, which is the basis of teaching mathematics, Pedagogy, psychology, teaching mathematics number.

In kindergarten and the primary grades to teach mathematics and science among the competition.

The fundamental functions of mathematical physics and the development of imagination in children in kindergarten find the arifmetika explain the basics of composition, quantity, related to the development of teaching is the main condition of space and time to imagine. Subject of the content in each lesson instructional technique reveals the main issues and life lessons to work in it. Thus, it should be borne in mind that, towards suggestions usually be given to children, assignments, exercises, questions are a typical example of. The number of such exercises, taking into account the specific conditions of the working class with the teacher, must determine independently. Extensive use of didactic materials for

teaching children in a large group is characterized by guidelines. Practical work, assignments that are also associated with the organization of the exhibition can be regarded as samples. The teacher is the guide at them-the guide may enter work under the correct account. In many cases, as recommended in oral exercises of the material give the teacher different options, depending on the preparation of the class while sometimes you can substitute. The teacher recommended a creative approach to the didactic game as you have to. Thus, used in the conduct of the game, considering the specific functions of each lesson, you can use the game itself.

Taylorlov mathematical methods we teach in groups

The preparatory group of the kindergarten two a week, is planning to conduct sessions in a year 72-74. Classes are held from September to the end of may 25-30 minutes from each one. Didactic training games, extensive use of visual materials.

Interested in training caregivers to children to participate must comply with the following requirements:

1 program of the material can be mastered better.

2 Thorough material (the show and newsletters) to prepare.

By changing their behavioral activity of 3 children to stand and pay attention.

Planning to hold harakatli 4 games between sessions.

Reach of the children during lessons concluded that 5 can stay independent.

Stimulation of the diverse response of 6 children.

Children's knowledge and skills to classes in the allocation of program materials, you should pay attention to their preparation. To know the correct use of special terms is of great importance. For example, the number and the concept of mix should not send. "Which a large number of small which" is asked. (a large number of which I can't say.) All the children in classes in order to achieve the active

participation of each child in front of the signal with the cards in a number of handouts is recommended. Thus, I will try to answer all the children listen carefully to the movement of a partner, is not a violation of discipline, preparation for testing the same children should also be taken into account.

To become familiar with numbers from 0 to 9.

Number – the number of the conditional sign. Understand the number of children number of additional, auxiliary stage. O'rgatilmaydi kids to write numbers only with the appearance of the print is introduced. The number of children which each number is the mark of all that there are a number of separate 10: 0,1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9. There is number 10. 10 the number of two numbers: 1 and 0 is determined. For example, in one lesson to become familiar with one or two numbers “1” to put the toy sanoq the number of caregivers in one acquainted with the cards, and cards with 1 puts their ranges to him.

He called 2 children, jump and one times two to the table once a man had two sons taqqillatishni offers. Children listed, than one that all of xuKeyin “1” indicating the number of this example is a mark of showing number, each number has its own icon that tushchuntiradi. Starting with the class that competition among kindergarten children to fill one of these iboratki by stack-stack, by tag put the tag up, listed by a collection of equally, science will determine Tfrom pointing signs in the science determining the relationship most of the characters are used.

Which are more in number, which number is less? Number 6 is less than 5, 5 to <6, to ensure equality inequality from what you need to do is ask. Adding 1 is generated and isolated birni equality barobarni understand the way to writethat is. 6=6...

Mathematics in the primary school o'qitishmetodlari

Arifmetik constitute the main content of the course material. The primary pivot of the main natural course shall consist of the number and amount arifmetika the main network. In addition, this course is a combination of the basic concepts of geometry and algebra. The school of mathematics primary school mathematics course, of course, the organic part. V–XI and mathematical technique is taught in the most basic class is due to the physics of a fundamental concept of the age of the pupils will be given. In the upper class, the same concepts with enhanced, extended and enriched without reading. Therefore, the primary school mathematics-its content drives high-grade in both mathematics content is identified. The structure of the specific properties of elementary mathematics has:

1 Arifmetik make up the main content of the course material. The amount of the main network, it arifmetika natural numbers, algebra and geometry of the element to read with the main courses propedivtik o'qitilmasdan arifmetik be in the form of material is added.

Concentric 2 primary class of material configured. For example, before-after reading ten numbering issues, then the numbering and complete actions in 100 arifmetik read. 1000 arifmetik then perform actions, then the number of a lot of room. Numbering to read them, along with the amount of knew, fractions, and geometric updated and expanded to read the materials is added.

We bound 3 the interaction of theory and practice in organic xarahas terga.

4 mathematical concepts, the texture, the opening moves in the course of mutual legally bound link.

5 local development without each concept is explained. For example, before I read the exact steps then its essence arifmetik the texture of your activities, then the connection between the components, then the result follow the connection between the actions is given at the end.

6 basic concepts and the resulting mutual understanding given in connection.

For example, the post on the basis of increase have been produced. Elementary mathematics on the structure of their course, containing arifmetik, updated and expanded material and geometric parts. Initial arifmetik in the mathematics course are stored in concentric location of the material. However, in the current program reduced the number of the concentric: ten, the face I have minglik, a lot of room number. Also have to say that the material guruhlash so great, then mutually linked concepts, actions, placed near the time to look at issues in all respects.

Arifmetik activities and corresponding calculation methods of the properties that have been arifmetik with the results of the study of the links between actions at a time with komponenta will reveal. (For example, if losing one of qo'shiluvchi the summary from the second qo'shiluvchi is formed.) Arifmetik actions change the results of one of the components that change is observed. Add elements of algebra, deep, understood and mastering umumlashgan the purpose is to answer: equality, inequality, equations, variables on the basis of the concept of konkret is revealed. 1-from the class number as well as the disparity equal ($4=4$, $6=1+5$, $2<3$, $6+1>5$, $8-3<8-2$ etc.) is considered.

Arifmetik learn them more deeply connected with the study of material and will help to reveal it. 2 from class- $(x+6)-3=2$ and h.see k wholesale of equations is considered. Tenglamalarni before charging with the selection of the method, then the results that have been practice with the components is made on the basis of birth know the link between moves.

Functional variables allows readers to check with practical imagination to occupy. Simple geometric geometric material figura most of the children become familiar with the development of their spatial imagination, as well as arifmetik qonuniyat, the link serves moves ko'rsatmali goals. (Masalan, both from the increased role of the right frame image to be equal to bind the texture of replacing kvadratga ko'rsatmali open to use...).

1-from the class of straight and curved lines, the incision, and their ko'pburchak elements, and on the corner hokozi included. Imagine geometric figura students to get them names, they need to learn to yasashlar soda katakli paper. In addition, the length of the incision and the broken line, the perimeter of ko'pburchak, rectangular, square, and in general the face of any figura (paletka using our skills to find the position you should take.

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